

Is Quantum Entropy Momentum-centric?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 10, 2020

Quantum entropy density is often written in the literature as: $-\int [W^*W] \ln[W^*W] - \int [a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $a(p)$ its Fourier transform. Thus, the entropy is written in a symmetric way in terms of momentum and position. Recently, we suggested in (2) that quantum entropy density should be written as: $-2 \int W dW/dx - \int [a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ which is no longer symmetric. In fact, the first term integrated over x yields 1 for any wavefunction. Thus, the entropy is really based on momentum. In this note, we investigate whether there is any reason to expect entropy should be symmetric in x and p . In classical statistical mechanics, where there may also be a spatial density due to $V(x)$, equilibrium (described by a temperature T) is based on two particle scattering i.e on momentum considerations. In classical physics, changes in momentum due to forces is the main consideration. In quantum mechanics, we argue that interactions with a stochastic potential (which is $V(x)$ on average) is the main driving force of “equilibrium” and that such reactions affect momentum. The spatial density is a consequence of these momentum effects and so we argue that it seems that there is no reason to consider x and p on the same footing in an expression for entropy density, even though the Heisenberg uncertainty principle also treats Δx and Δp on an equal footing. We investigate these and other issues in this note.

Influence of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle for Δx and Δp

The Heisenberg uncertainty principle: $\Delta x \Delta p \leq \hbar/2$, where Δx and Δp are variances over all x and p , is symmetric in x and p . Furthermore, the standard argument in quantum textbooks seems to be: If position is known exactly, momentum is completely unknown and vice versa. This symmetry and splitting of x and p seems to fit well with the entropy density expression: $-\int [W^*W] \ln[W^*W] - \int [a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ ((1)) often used in the literature. In the case of the quantum oscillator, the integral of the first term over x and the second over p (one dimension) are very similar. Thus, not only is there symmetry at the density level, but both terms contribute to the overall entropy.

In a previous note (2), we argued one should use: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) + a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$, which is a probability addend in the expression for $W(x)W(x)$ (for the bound case), in Shannon’s entropy. This leads to an entropy density: $-2 \int W dW/dx - \int [a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ ((2)) which is not symmetric in p and x . Furthermore, the first term integrated over x yields 1 for all wavefunctions $W(x)$. Thus, the strictly momentum portion of the entropy density gives the main contribution to overall entropy, although the spatial $W(x)$ and momentum $a(p)$ pieces contribute to the entropy density, although in an unsymmetric manner. Thus, we ask: Is there any reason to believe that quantum entropy density should be symmetric in x and p ?

Classical Statistical Mechanics

It seems classical statistical mechanics (e.g. the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution) may be described in terms of a balanced two particle reaction i.e.

$$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{with } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \text{ where } f(e) \text{ is the distribution function}$$

Taking the ln of the latter and linking to the former yields the MB distribution. Thus, the “statistics” are related to physical scattering i.e. to momentum. If there is a potential $V(x)$, e_1 changes from $p_1^2/2m$ to $p_1^2/2m + V(x)$ because each single particle moves classically within the potential until it collides. The collisions, however, drive the equilibrium. If one has quantum particles such as fermions or bosons, ((3)) changes to: $f(e_1)[1 \mp f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1 \mp f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1 \mp f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1 \mp f(e_2)]$ ((4)). Thus, collisions again govern the statistical picture.

Bound State Quantum Problem

In analogy, we argue that if one considers a quantum particle in a potential, if this a statistical system there should be microscopic momentum states which interact with the stochastic potential: $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. One again has a momentum situation, however, the stochastic nature is due to the stochastic potential which depends on x . One may suggest a momentum distribution at each x : $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the normalization constant which depends on x (which is also the wavefunction). One essentially has a momentum picture, but x is part of the probability to have a certain momentum x . Ultimately, this leads to a spatial density, but there is also a spatial density in the classical statistical mechanical case if there is a $V(x)$. At this point, it does not seem there is any reason to argue that momentum and spatial entropy density terms should be of the same form. In fact, we argue one should base entropy strictly on momentum probabilities. The spatial density is given by $\sum p_1, p_2 a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ so we argue that the addend probabilities are the ones to use in Shannon's entropy. In this picture, one need not consider a spatial entropy term at all. One may leave all terms in the form of: $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ products. “X” appears because it is part of the momentum probability.

Phase Space Issues

In classical statistical mechanics, one deals with a momentum- x phase space which is based on the simultaneous knowledge of x, p values of a particle. In quantum mechanics, it is often argued that one may not know momentum and position exactly at any given time. If one uses complex probabilities, however, one has a momentum distribution at each x , based on possible p values and x i.e.

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) allows one to calculate the average momentum and kinetic energy at a point i.e. $\langle KE \rangle = \frac{\sum p^2 a(p) \exp(ipx)}{W(x)}$. $\langle KE \rangle$, however, is not a physical observable. It is interesting to note that using $P(p/x)P(x) = P(p \text{ and } x)$ ((6)) where $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ in Shannon's entropy leads to an entropy density of the form $-\frac{1}{W} \sum [W^*W \ln(W^*W) - a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)]] - W \frac{dW}{dx}$. Thus, there is some symmetry between x and p in this scenario, but also an additional term. This seems to be analogous in form to the classical statistical case where one also has a probability $P(p \text{ and } x)$ given the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

The issue we have with ((6)) is that $P(x)$ is an ensemble average and it seems entropy should not be based on ensemble values. It seems it is the actual stochastic motion of the particle, or distribution of its momentum in space that is important. The issue does not occur in classical statistical mechanics as one does not use $P(p/x)$ because two body collisions rather than a stochastic potential $V(x) = V(k) \exp(ikx)$ cause the equilibrium.

The spatial density, which is a physical observable, is the sum of "and" relative probability combinations $a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$. These seem to be the microscopic driver of the statistical equilibrium. One may ask why one should have two momenta in a little region dx . It seems that $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ yields stochastic hits within dx so that the momentum distribution changes from x to $x+dx$. If the momentum distribution changes, then the average kinetic energy changes from x to $x+dx$ according to $E = V(x)$. Thus, in quantum bound systems, one has two momenta p_1, p_2 for each x . Thus, this is an unusual phase space, very different from that of classical statistical mechanics where one has one p at each x to $x+dx$.

To see this another way, consider $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. At $x+dx$, the distribution is: $P(p/(x+dx)) = a(p) \exp(ip(x+dx)) / W(x+dx)$. Thus, there is a change in relative momentum probabilities at x and $x+dx$. One may ask how the distribution of p can change as one moves from x to $x+dx$. If interactions are all that are present, one may argue that a particle in p_1 at x changes to p_2 with x and $x+dx$. Note: $\exp(ipx)$ is part of the probability, not a physical wave in these equations. Thus, one needs to specify two momenta for each x .

Constant Momentum Variance at x

$$\text{Consider: } \langle p \rangle = g(x) = -i \frac{d}{dx} W / W = \frac{\sum p a(p) \exp(ipx)}{W(x)} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, the variance squared of $\langle p \rangle$ at x is given by:

$$\langle p^2 \rangle - \langle p \rangle^2 = - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W} + \left(\frac{dW/dx}{W} \right)^2 = C1 \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{And } \frac{d}{dx} \left[-i \frac{dW/dx}{W} \right] = -i \left\{ - \left(\frac{dW/dx}{W} \right) \left(\frac{dW/dx}{W} \right) + \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W} \right\} \quad ((9))$$

Combining ((8)) and ((9)) yields:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{dW/dx}{W} \right] = -C1 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{dW/dx}{W} = -C1 x \quad ((10))$$

This implies that $W(x) = C \exp(-a x^2)$, a Gaussian and also the wavefunction of the ground state quantum oscillator. $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ is also a Gaussian. A Gaussian, however, implies random motion from the Central Limit Theorem. Thus, one would expect that $-[WW] \ln[WW]$ might represent spatial entropy for the ground state oscillator, as $P(x)$ is an independent random variable in this special case. This value is identical to $-2 \int W x dW/dx$ from the $a(p1) \exp(ip1 x)$ $a(p2) \exp(ip2 x)$ approach, but only for the gs oscillator.

In other cases, the entropy density depends on x time $\langle p \rangle$ which is a function of x . This term, however, integrates over x to 1, so the overall entropy is based on the integral of momentum entropy density.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue there is no reason to expect entropy density to be symmetric in x and p because the quantum bound state equilibrium is based on momentum scattering with a stochastic potential $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$. Unlike the classical statistical case, the momentum distribution at each x is x dependent (in addition to utilizing complex probabilities). Because this momentum distribution must change from x to $x+dx$ so that $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)=E$, we argue that in each dx around x , an initial momentum state of p_i must change into p_j . Thus, we argue the important momentum related probability is: $a(p_i) \exp(i p_i x) a(p_j) \exp(i p_j x)$ which we use in Shannon's entropy. If one wishes to have a system with a constant variance at each x for $\langle p \rangle = -i dW/dx / W$, then $\langle p \rangle$ is proportional to x and $W=C \exp(-ax^2)$. This is a Gaussian which implies random positioning according to the Central Limit Theorem. Thus, we argue that the spatial portion of entropy from $a(p_i) \exp(i p_i x) a(p_j) \exp(i p_j x)$, namely $-2 \int W x dW/dx$ should equal $-[WW] \ln[WW]$ for this special case, namely the ground state of quantum oscillator and it does. For other cases, one does not have $-[WW] \ln[WW]$, but there is still $a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)]$. Thus, the symmetry between x and p only holds for this one special case of the ground state oscillator.

References

1. Majernik, V and Opatrny Entropic Uncertainty Relations For a Quantum Oscillator (J. Phys. A Math 1996) <http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relationship Between Entropy and Energy Densities in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2020)